
IMPERATIVES OF ADOPTING CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: A THEORETICAL REVIEW

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Abstract

The adoption of Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) and adapting to climate change mitigation measures in agricultural practices are some of the interventions in many parts of the world which have impacted positively on the environment and is yielding successes in crop productivity, food security and sustainable development, with resultant reduction of Green House Gases (GHGs) emissions and manifestation of extreme temperature outcomes including flood, drought and erosion, among others. This theoretical paper examines the significance of CSA in the social and cultural integration of the Nigerian society. The sociological approach was adopted in the study with suggestions on the way forward.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Climate, Agriculture, Climate Smart Agriculture

Introduction

The term Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) was defined by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations at the Hague Conference on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change in 2010. The aim was to contribute to the development of agriculture and food security in a holistic and sustainable way, by integrating economic, social and environmental aspects into agriculture and food security process. The main pillars of the CSA concept defined by the FAO include:

1. Sustainably increasing agricultural productivity and incomes

2. Adapting and building resilience to climate change
3. Reducing and/or removing greenhouse gases emissions (GHGs), where possible.

Many agrarian societies particularly among developing nations such as Nigeria have been faced with climate change challenges due to non-integration of the economic, social and environmental aspects into agriculture and food security process.

As a result of land scarcity and in a quest to satisfy the increasing demand for food in an increasing population, particularly in the post-COVID era, farmers in many agrarian societies resort to shortened cycle of shifting cultivation; repetitive cultivation; bush burning and cultivation of land with steep cliff among other practices that are considered counterproductive to the achievement of CSA and its objectives. While shortened cycle of shifting cultivation for instance results in excess chemicals in the soil and underground water contamination due to continuous use of inorganic fertilizer to improve the already impoverished and nutrient depleted soil, bush burning increases the level of GHGs emission, and cultivation of land with steep cliff increases the amount and speed of surface run-off which escalates the menace of erosion. There are many smart farming techniques which if adapted, can facilitate the achievement of benefits derivable from CSA, including conservation farming which helps keep soils from eroding, preserves land fertility and saves local plant and animal life; smart water management which conserves water supplies by lowering unnecessary water consumption; mulching and wind-breaks which keeps the soil covered in order to reduce moisture loss, stabilizes soil temperature, reduces erosion by water and wind, restores soil carbon through the decomposition of crop residues, and provides food for beneficial soil organisms.

The purpose of this paper is to increase the level of awareness and compliance on adoption of climate smart agriculture model in agricultural practices in Nigeria and adapting to climate change mitigation measures in order to achieve sustainable development through food security.

Climate smart agriculture is an integrated approach to managing land to help adapt agricultural methods, livestock and crops to the effects of climate change and where possible counteract it by relying on eco-friendly methods to mitigate environmental damages. Climate smart agriculture concept reflects the ambition to improve the integration of agricultural development and climate responsiveness. As an approach, CSA helps the people who manage agricultural systems respond effectively to climate change.

It aims to achieve food security and broader development goals under a changing climate and increasing food demand. The CSA approach helps guide actions to transform agri-food systems towards green and climate resilient practices.

Climate change is one of the main challenges facing agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa region where many rely only on rain-fed farming for their livelihoods (Kurukulasuriya *et al.*, 2006). Climate change is also seen as constituting new challenges to the fight against poverty and sustainability of agrarian livelihoods in sub-Saharan Africa. Predictions indicate that climate change will adversely affect agricultural production in sub-Saharan Africa through declining crop yields and livestock productivity caused by rainfall variability, rising temperatures and increased pest/disease incidences (Kurukulasuriya & Rosenthal, 2003). Moreover, Lobell *et al.* (2011) posited that climate change is likely to cause considerable crop yield losses thereby adversely affecting smallholder livelihoods in Africa, the outcome of which food security and income generation opportunities for the farming households that are most reliant on agriculture would be greatly jeopardized.

CSA implementation uses technical solutions, policies and financing mechanisms to cover all sectors of agriculture including crops, livestock, fisheries, and forestry (Lipper *et al.*, 2014). This includes some common sustainable agricultural techniques, such as agroforestry, conservation agriculture, integrated crop-livestock systems, or aspects such as improved water management, weather forecasting and risk insurances (Nepad, 2014).

According to FAO (2013), CSA as an approach, is targeted at developing countries and small holders, but the principles can equally be applied to

agriculture in developed countries, which are faced with the same problems: emissions of GHGs from agriculture, threat by climate change, and population growth.

CSA is not a single specific agricultural technology or practice that can be universally applied; rather it is a set of measures that can be adapted to specific cases and contexts. Although the term CSA might be relatively new, the practices applied to achieve the goals are not necessarily new. In some cases, the adaptation of simple and long-known practices, or a combination of practices that have been unknown to the respective farmer might be climate smart.

CSA, Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability – Global Assessment

Since its inception as an approach to guide the management of agriculture in the era of climate change, CSA has been reshaped through inputs and interactions of multiple stakeholders such as food security and climate change experts, agricultural research institutes and relevant NGOs which are involved in developing and implementing the concept. CSA aims to provide globally applicable principles on managing agriculture for food security under climate change that could provide the basis for policy support and recommendations by multilateral organisations, such as UN and FAO.

The major features of the CSA approach were developed in response to limitations in the international climate policy arena in the understanding of agriculture's role in food security and its potential for capturing synergies between adaptation and mitigation (Farauta *et al.*, 2011). Recent controversies which have arisen over CSA are rooted in longstanding debates in both the climate and sustainable agricultural development policy spheres. These include the role of developing countries, and specifically their agricultural sectors in reducing global GHG emissions, as well as the choice of technologies which may best promote sustainable forms of agriculture (FAO, 2015).

Since the term 'CSA' was widely adopted before the development of a formal

conceptual frame and tools to implement the approach, there has been considerable variation in meanings applied to the term, which also contributed to manifestation of diverse controversies. As the body of work on the concept, methods, tools and applications of the CSA approach expands, it is becoming clearer what it can offer. Ultimately, CSA's utility will be judged by its effectiveness in integrating climate change response into sustainable agricultural development strategies on the ground.

Climate change has fundamentally altered the agricultural development agenda, not only in Nigeria but around the world. This becomes manifest through changing temperature and precipitation, sea level rise and the frequency of extreme climatic conditions which already impact negatively on agricultural production globally (Medugu *et al.*, 2012). Many cases including the unanticipated heavy snows in New York and other cities of the United States, wild fires in Alaska area of Mexico, heavy flooding in many provinces in China; India, Korea, Sydney in Australia, and South Africa; the drought of Northern Italy, as well as parts of East and Central Africa, among others, have been reported in recent times. All these constitute climate risks to agricultural production and sustainable development. According to FAO (2010), climate risks to crops, livestock and fisheries are expected to increase in coming decades, particularly in low-income countries where adaptive capacity is weaker.

The impacts of climate change on agriculture threaten both food security and agriculture's pivotal role in rural livelihoods sustenance and broad-based development. Therefore, the effect of agricultural production on the environment must be given attention so that an attempt to proffer solution to food scarcity through the provision of more food will not turn out a negative impact on the environment. This is why Foley *et al.* (2011) cautioned that attempt to meet the needs of a growing population through increased food production must be achieved with minimum impacts on the environment. Adapting agriculture to climate change is necessary to achieve food security, and has potentials to contribute to low emissions development strategies (Branca *et al.*, 2011).

Climate Smart Agriculture is an integrated approach to achieve food security in the face of climate change, while also mitigating climate change impacts and contributing to other development goals (FAO, 2013). Since the emergence of CSA model, a large variety of climate smart systems have been developed all over the world, especially at the community level (FAO, 2013). It has been noted that developing sustainable food systems which are resilient to climate change and have a reduced carbon footprint requires specific and coordinated action from all stakeholders in the food system (Ingram, 2011). Farmers in countries like Niger, Kenya, and Algeria have successfully adopted climate smart agriculture which usually includes farm-based sustainable agricultural land management practices such as conservation tillage, agroforestry, and residue management, but they also need to use other climate smart technologies such as early warning systems and crop insurances.

Currently, much attention is directed towards up-scaling and out-scaling successful CSA practices and technologies to other areas with similar agro-ecological and institutional conditions so they can have a substantive impact on food security, climate change resilience and mitigation (Kipkoech *et al.*, 2015). Up-scaling or scaling-up means bringing more quality benefits to more people over a wider geographical area, more quickly and equitably, while out-scaling or scaling-out means extending and expanding the scope of successful climate smart technologies to areas where such benefits can make substantial impact.

Relationship between Agriculture, CSA and Rural Development

CSA describes agricultural practices aimed at adapting to climate change and mitigating the impact of climate on agriculture while maintaining and increasing productivity. Rural development has traditionally centered on the exploitation of land-intensive natural resources such as agriculture and forestry, but it also involves efforts that are economic and social in nature, intended to encourage concepts of retention, growth, and expansion in areas outside cities, including improving quality of life for rural residents through such activity (Ogbalubi & Wokocha, 2013). Rural development as the process involving the progressive activity or positive social change that takes place in the rural environment is significant due to its capacity to improve the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in rural areas (or relatively

isolated and sparsely populated areas).

There are various types of approaches to rural development including: Sectoral Approach, Area Development Approach, Integrated Development Approach, Growth Center Approach and Community-Driven Development (CDD) Approach. However, a combination of the Integrated Development Approach and Community-Driven Development Approach has been seen to be more germane in CSA.

Agriculture and rural development are related in such a way that the latter is reinforced by the earlier, since the dominant occupational and economic activities that propel rural development is agriculture. The rural sector contributes more to the emission of GHGs and other factors that aggravate the negative outcomes of non-adoption of climate smart agricultural practices.

Challenges in Achieving Climate Smart Agriculture

One of the challenges in achieving the goals of climate smart agriculture is the capacity to develop innovative business models to ensure appropriate and timely distribution and exchange of climate smart products. As observed in Westermann *et al.* (2018), the capacity to develop insights into effectiveness of different approaches for scaling up promising pilot initiatives has been a key challenge in climate smart agricultural research. Innovative business development platforms for moving to scale and different approaches for scaling up climate smart agriculture are being continually tested including scaling up through agricultural extension services, participatory approaches, climate smart villages (CSV) and approaches based on value chains and private sector involvement.

Developing and defining innovative business models and innovation platforms for scaling climate smart agriculture practices should focus on scaling through climate smart business development. It should seek to link farmers' needs and climate smart farm products to private sector interests as a novel way of moving to scale (Westermann *et al.*, 2018). Farmers who are interested in the use of climate smart technologies and/or producing climate smart products

should be supported to access new markets and operate in highly dynamic market environments just as agro-food chains and networks play an increasingly important role in providing access to markets for smallholder farmers (Ruben *et al.*, 2006).

There are several challenges associated with this development especially for rural smallholder farmers and producers. These challenges include attainment of standards through quality control measures, engagement with food chains and network groups, and capacity to move toward globally interconnected systems with a large variety of complex relationships, and supply reliability demands by customers e.g., supermarkets. These challenges are further aggravated by the lack of resources and inputs, high transaction costs and inefficient infrastructure and services. Though smallholder farmers are seemingly well placed to take part in the new markets that are being created, in part due to their strong historical agricultural tradition, which naturally favours agro-climatic conditions and relatively low labour costs; considerably, few smallholder farmers are participating in food chains and networks. According to Ruben *et al.*, (2006), inclusion of small-scale farmers in coordinated supply chains mainly depends on:

- (1) farmers' understanding of markets and economic opportunities;
- (2) willingness of private entrepreneurs to work with them;
- (3) perceived benefits, costs, and risks and,
- (4) enabling laws, regulations and policies.

Indeed, business contributions to sustainable development are founded in new types of business models. These new business models emphasize interactions between individuals, groups and organisations, and focus more on building networks and collaborative practices for learning and relearning new visions, concepts and values which are socially constructed while unlearning old questionable values that are not positive.

Social and Economic Importance of Adopting Climate Smart Agriculture

Adoption of climate smart agriculture has physical, social and economic benefits which can positively impact the social and physical environment in

several ways. First, CSA contributes to green and clean environment and is capable of impacting the ecosystem in general. In particular, the food chain at each level of the food system is affected, thereby making adaptation imperative so as to mitigate the impacts of climate change and its chain effects on the environment. As all stages of the food value chain will likely be affected by extreme climate events associated with climate change, it requires taking short term and long term adaptive measures. For example, sea level change from climate change over time may affect ports (Ruben *et al.*, 2006), and extreme weather events could damage both roads and other facilities used throughout the post-production stages of food value chains.

Climate smart agriculture can sustainably increase agricultural productivity and incomes; promote adaptation and build resilience to climate change; reduce or remove greenhouse gases, and can be used to address food shortages using a food systems approach.

CSA promotes intervention that applies to multiple stages of food value chains and multiple levels of the food system, including reducing food loss and waste and increasing efficiency in the use of resources.

Food loss and waste not only squanders the resources used in agricultural production across food value chains, such as inputs like irrigation water, fertilizers, time and energy, it also represents a major source of greenhouse gases. According to the European Commission's Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research, the total carbon footprint of food loss and waste is around 4.4 gigatonnes of carbon dioxide equivalence per year, or about 8 percent of the total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (FAO, 2015).

Along with food loss and waste, the efficient use of resources (e.g. fertilizers, water, and energy) is a cross-cutting issue that applies to all levels of the food system and all stages of the food value chains. At the production stage, improving efficiency in the use of inputs through sustainable intensification can deliver both adaptation and mitigation benefits by;

1. promoting sustainable soil management practice to improve carbon storage, which is applicable in conservation agriculture.
2. improving fertilizer application practices to increase fertilizer-use efficiency.
3. improving water-use efficiency through alternative wetting as in the case of irrigation and second season watering of crops.
4. reducing food loss and waste through improved coordination within a regulated food chain.
5. promoting conservation agriculture and sustainable mechanization.
6. utilizing improved seed varieties that are adapted to climate change (e.g. drought-resistant, heat tolerant and flood tolerant).

As noted earlier, the objectives of climate smart agriculture include to sustainably increase agricultural productivity and incomes; adapt and build resilience to climate change and reduce and/or remove greenhouse gas emissions, where possible.

Way Forward

In the view of Westermann *et al.*, (2018), multi stakeholder innovation platforms to facilitate interaction and encourage farmers' inclusion in food chains for sustainable development must be promoted. In order to achieve this, climate smart villages where representatives of farmers' cooperative groups can interact should be structured. There is need to build climate smart villages which are sites where researchers from national and international organisations, farmers' cooperatives, local government, community leaders, private sector organisations and key policy planners work together on climate smart agriculture interventions that are most appropriate to tackle the climate challenges in the agriculture sector. The structure must be systematic and well-coordinated in order to function optimally.

The climate smart village adopts a portfolio of interventions that cover the full spectrum of farm activities, service suppliers, researchers, policy makers, market and retail parties to co-create climate smart business models. Such intervention is expected to help in developing and defining innovative

business models and open innovation platforms for scaling climate smart agriculture practices which works to enhance the achievement of national food security and development goals. These platforms provide farmers with opportunities to learn about new markets and how to access value-adding technologies for their goods and products. The more organised farmers are, the better their bargaining power and the more they are likely to benefit from agrobusinesses. Prohibitive laws, regulations and policies associated with value chain governance as well as other constraining factors including private sector actors, research institutions, government and the role it must play to support the development of climate-smart value chains for sustainable food systems should constitute discussions at the platform to reach positive actions.

Methodology

The study adopts the library research methodology with an extensive review of related literature from secondary sources while data was analyzed using content analysis. These sources in particular include books, journals and online sources. Extensive literature reviews yielded enormous data that have been found to be insightful and useful in drawing valid conclusion.

Conclusion

Multiple stakeholders from agricultural producers and associated groups including entrepreneurs, consumers, researchers and public officials at all levels of government have a role in shaping sustainable food systems. This is in line with the position of Ingram (2011), that developing sustainable food systems which are resilient to climate change and have a reduced carbon footprint will require specific and coordinated actions from all stakeholders in the food system. Other stakeholders including multilateral institutions will also enter an important role in this regard as they will be influential in encouraging global climate commitments, supporting governments in meeting national commitments in their development plans (e.g. nationally appropriate mitigation actions), and advocating for climate smart agriculture policies. Community based organisations and non-governmental organisations will also be instrumental in informing consumers and other stakeholders in the food system about options to reduce food loss and waste through training programmes, public awareness campaigns, etc.

Recommendations

1. There is need to build climate smart villages which are sites where researchers from national and international organisations, farmers' cooperatives, local government, community leaders, private sector organisations and key policy planners work together on climate smart agriculture interventions that are most appropriate to tackle the climate challenges in the agriculture sector. The structure must be systematic and well-coordinated in order to function optimally.
2. There is also need to develop and define innovative business models to facilitate up-scaling and out-scaling successful CSA practices and technologies to other areas with similar agro-ecological and institutional conditions so they can have a substantive impact on food security, climate change resilience and mitigation
3. It is imperative to open innovation platforms for scaling climate smart agriculture practices which works to enhance the achievement of national food security and development goals. These platforms provide farmers with opportunities to learn about new markets and how to access value adding technologies for goods and products.
4. Another imperative is the formation of community based organisations and non-governmental organisations to facilitate sensitization of consumers and other stakeholders in the food system about options to reduce food loss and waste, through training programmes, public awareness campaigns, etc.

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